

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-9

PHYSICAL TRAINING OF YOUTHS WITH THE MEANS OF ATHLETIC GYMNASTICS.

Teacher of the general military training cycle of the Faculty of Military Education of the Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute:

Haydarov Muzaffar Urmanovich

Abstract: This article analyzes the role of using athletic gymnastics equipment in improving the physical fitness of young people before conscription. It covers the content, main equipment, importance of athletic gymnastics in the life of young people before conscription, and principles of effective organization of training. The article pays special attention to the issues of raising young people to be healthy, strong and strong-willed, as well as increasing their readiness to defend the Motherland.

Keywords: Athletic gymnastics, physical training, strength, endurance, agility, youth, preparation for conscription, healthy lifestyle, defense of the Motherland.

Main part: Providing physical education to young people in the Republic of Uzbekistan is one of the priority areas of state policy. The physical fitness of boys before conscription is the main stage in preparing them for future service in the army, defense of the Motherland, and difficult life conditions. In this process, athletic gymnastics is one of the most effective tools, serving to strengthen the health of young people, increase strength and endurance, and cultivate willpower and discipline. Today, the importance of physical education and sports facilities in raising the youth of our country in a healthy and well-rounded manner is incomparable. Ensuring physical fitness through athletic gymnastics facilities, especially for boys of pre-conscription age, is one of the important directions of the state defense system.

Athletic gymnastics is a set of exercises performed using weights or body weight, which develops strength, endurance, agility and dexterity. Its main tools are:

- ✚ dumbbell and barbell exercises;
- ✚ horizontal bar and horizontal bar exercises;
- ✚ kettlebell and stone lifting exercises;
- ✚ bodyweight exercises such as sit-ups, squats, and jumps;
- ✚ combination exercises that combine strength, speed, and endurance.

Physical training tasks

The following main tasks are solved through the use of athletic gymnastics equipment:

- ❖ Developing muscle strength. Tasks such as lifting weights, long walks, and carrying equipment in military service require strong muscles.
- ❖ Increasing endurance. Adapting to being under load for a long time strengthens the health of young people.
- ❖ Developing agility and dexterity. Agility is important for quick action in military exercises and adapting to sudden situations.
- ❖ Improve health. Regular exercise strengthens the cardiovascular and respiratory systems, increases immunity.
- ❖ Form willpower and discipline. Regular performance of heavy exercises requires patience and willpower. These qualities are of great importance both in the army and in life.

Importance

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-9

Athletic gymnastics equipment plays an important role in the lives of young people:

- ✓ increases physical fitness for military service;
- ✓ establishes a healthy lifestyle;
- ✓ helps to get rid of harmful habits;
- ✓ strengthens willpower and mental stability.

Principles of organizing training

To effectively organize athletic gymnastics training, it is necessary to pay attention to the following:

- ✚ regular and systematic conduct of exercises;
- ✚ gradual increase in load;
- ✚ technically correct execution and compliance with safety;
- ✚ use of an individual approach;
- ✚ combination of strength exercises with general developmental exercises.

For athletic gymnastics training to be effective, the following rules are followed:

- ✓ Graduality - exercises are initially given in a light form, and then the load is gradually increased.
- ✓ Regularity - exercises should be performed at least 3-4 times a week.
- ✓ Comprehensive approach - along with strength exercises, running, jumping, and stretching exercises are also included.
- ✓ Individual approach - the health status and physical capabilities of each young person are taken into account.
- ✓ Technically correct execution - exercises should be performed under the supervision of a coach or teacher to avoid injuries.

Healthy competition, mutual cooperation, and adherence to sports discipline during training further strengthen the spiritual and willpower education of young people.

Conclusion: Improving the physical fitness of young people before conscription through athletic gymnastics is a process of great importance not only in sports, but also in social and spiritual terms. Because every young man going to military service must be strong, healthy, resilient and strong-willed. Athletic gymnastics helps to ensure all these requirements. Firstly, it increases muscle strength and endurance, which is important when lifting heavy loads, long walks and performing other physical tasks in military service. Secondly, athletic gymnastics, through regular training, strengthens the cardiovascular and respiratory systems, improves the general health of young people. This increases their resistance to diseases and ensures that they go to the army healthy. Thirdly, sports exercises develop willpower, discipline and patience. Regularly continuing the exercises, even if they are difficult, strengthens the psychological stability of young people, helps them become mentally strong and determined. Fourthly, athletic gymnastics teaches young people to lead a healthy lifestyle, encourages them to stay away from harmful habits. This increases their quality of life, contributes to their formation as active and useful individuals in society. Fifthly, such exercises develop teamwork, mutual assistance, and sports spirit. Healthy competition and cooperation are formed among young people. In conclusion, the use of athletic gymnastics equipment raises the physical fitness of young people to a high level before conscription, prepares them for the defense of the Motherland, and serves to form a healthy, strong and harmonious generation. Therefore, the widespread introduction of athletic gymnastics classes in secondary schools, colleges and lyceums, as well as sports clubs, is an urgent task today.

REFERENCES:

1. Karimov I.A. *Yuksak ma'naviyat – yengilmas kuch.* – Toshkent: Ma'naviyat, 2008.
2. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining "Jismoniy tarbiya va sportni rivojlantirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi farmonlari va qarorlari.
3. Xo'jayev M., Abduqodirov A. *Jismoniy tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi.* – Toshkent: O'qituvchi, 2016.
4. Axmedov R. *Sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi.* – Toshkent: O'zbekiston Yozuvchilar uyushmasi nashriyoti, 2019.
5. Internet manbalari: www.olympic.uz, www.sportedu.uz

